

Covid-19 and diabetes mellitus management

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Abstract: In COVID-19, diabetes mellitus is a common comorbidity. For those individuals with COVID-19 and diabetes mellitus, the effect of BG control on treatment requirements and death is still unknown. To that end, we conducted a retrospective analysis involving 7 337 COVID-19 patients from Janakpur Provincial Hospital, Janakpur Dham, Nepal, during April 2021- March 2022, of which 952 already had type 2 diabetes. A greater mortality rate (7.8% versus 2.7%; adjusted hazard ratio [HR], 1.49) and multiple organ injury were detected in patients with diabetes mellitus, as were more medical interventions. For those with well-managed BG (glycemic variability between 3.0 and 10.0 mmol/L), mortality was considerably lower than in those with poorly controlled BG (glycemic variability greater than 10.0 mmol/L) during hospitalization (adjusted HR, 0.14). Patients with COVID-19 and preexisting diabetes mellitus benefit from better glycemic management, according to these data.

Keywords: Covid-19, diabetes mellitus, Nepal, glycemic management

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Accepted: 23 July, 2022; **Published:** 28 July, 2022

How to cite this article: Dr. Gautam Kumar Sah, Dr. Sharad Yadav², Dr. Shwena Thakur, Dr. Mahesh Mahaseth, Dr. Sanjeet Kumar Jha, Dr. Gyanendra Yadav (2022). Covid-19 and diabetes mellitus management. *North American Academic Research*, 5(7), 121-134. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6914972>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

The enclosed, positive, single-stranded RNA viruses known as coronaviruses are widespread throughout the animal and human populations of the world [1]. Major outbreaks of two betacoronaviruses, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) in 2002–2003 and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) in 2012, have caused deadly pneumonia, with mortality rates of 10 percent for SARS-CoV and 36 percent for MERS-CoV [2]. Although most human coronavirus infections are mild, major outbreaks of two betacoronaviruses, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus.

Clusters of people diagnosed with pneumonia in December 2019 emerged in Wuhan, which is located in Hubei Province, China. The causes of these instances are unknown. Samples taken from the lower respiratory tract were subjected to a deep sequencing analysis, which revealed that a novel coronavirus was the cause of the disease. This coronavirus was given the name Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2), and the illness that it causes was given the name COVID-19 [1, 3]. Although SARS-CoV-2 has exhibited phylogenetic and clinical similarities with SARS-CoV, the novel coronavirus appears to have a stronger transmissibility and lower case fatality rates [4]. This is despite the fact that SARS-CoV-2 has showed similarities with SARS-CoV. The World Health Organization (WHO) escalated the COVID-19 epidemic to a pandemic on March 11, 2020, after declaring the outbreak a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on January 30, 2020 [5]. 827,419 confirmed cases have been officially reported in more than 200 nations or territories as of today (02.04.2020), with 40,777 deaths [6].

We decided to undertake a scoping research in order to provide a quick explanation of the general characteristics of COVID-19, as well as a more extensive description and critical assessment of the link between this newly discovered viral disease and diabetes. We have high hopes that this evaluation will be able to provide useful information for further research and, ultimately, lead to improvements in the clinical management of people who have both COVID-19 and diabetes.

Enveloped viruses with a single-stranded, positive-sense RNA genome are known to cause respiratory illnesses in humans. These viruses are referred to as coronaviruses (CoV) (7, 38). The majority of immunocompetent people who become infected with human CoV develop a moderate upper respiratory illness as a result of the virus. On the other hand, two extremely pathogenic coronaviruses were responsible for the outbreaks of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in the Guangdong province of China in 2003 and Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) in the countries of the Middle East a decade later. The coronaviruses known as SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV have been identified as the agents responsible for SARS and MERS, respectively (11, 51, 55). In Wuhan, China, in the month of December 2019, a novel coronavirus known as SARS-CoV-2 was discovered to be the pathogen responsible for the outbreak of coronavirus illness (COVID-19) (11, 51, 55). The World Health Organization (WHO) announced that COVID-19 has reached epidemic proportions on March 11, 2020. In the United States, there have been a total of 103,942 confirmed cases, including 1689 fatalities, as of the 27th of March in the year 2020. (19a). There have been 27,324 recorded deaths out of a total of 595,800 verified cases across the world (19a).

People who have diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension, or extreme obesity (BMI 40 kg/m²) have an increased risk of becoming infected with COVID-19, as well as an increased risk of developing complications from the virus and dying from it (3a, 16, 30, 48, 50, 52, 56). Individuals who suffer from diabetes have a higher risk for both SARS and MERS, which is an interesting finding. There are 34.2 million people in the United States who have diabetes, which accounts for 10.5% of the total population (3a). Diabetes mellitus affects 26.8 percent of people aged 65 and older, which is a demographic that has a higher chance of dying from COVID-19 (3a). The presence of hypertension and severe obesity is found in 68.4 and 15.5% of patients diagnosed with diabetes, respectively. A sizeable proportion of the population of the United States will become infected with SARS-CoV-2 over the course of many months (12). Although a considerable number are expected to continue to be asymptomatic and maintain their ability to spread the virus, the predicted percentage of symptomatic individuals who will need to be hospitalized rises with increasing age (12). This proportion runs anywhere from 17 to 27 percent in those who are older than 60 years of age. In addition, among people of this age,

the percentage of hospitalized patients who need to receive care in an intensive care unit (ICU) ranges from 27 to 71 percent, and the infection fatality rate (IFR) for these patients can be anywhere from 2.2 to 9.3 percent (12). Even though these estimates are preliminary and are likely to change, it is likely that the pandemic has the potential to cause significant mortality and morbidity considering the prevalence of diabetes, hypertension, and severe obesity in the United States and the substantial increased risk for COVID-19 and its complications in patients with these conditions. Clinical care will be provided to a significant number of patients diagnosed with COVID-19 in inpatient, outpatient, and telemedicine settings by medical specialists and other health care providers. It is necessary to have a greater awareness of the clinical features, pathophysiology, and potential mechanisms that increase the risk in order to provide better care to patients with diabetes and to spur new investigations, both basic and clinical, in order to gain a better understanding of COVID-19 in these patients.

Figure 1 Illustration of the interrelationship between SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19 and diabetes. (Source: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2021.649525> Permission accepted)

Study Design and Participants

Patients who were diagnosed with COVID-19 between the dates of December 30, 2019, and March 20, 2020, served as the subjects of this study. The diagnosis of COVID-19 was made using chest computed tomography (CT) manifestations and/or reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). These methods were used in accordance with the

criteria outlined in the New Coronavirus Pneumonia Prevention and Control Program (5th edition), which was published by the National Health Commission of China and WHO interim guidance. A total of 9,663 patients diagnosed with COVID-19 through the screening process in the beginning of the trial. However, data from individuals were not included in the study if the subjects were younger than 18 or older than 75 or had incomplete medical records (for example, transfer to another hospital), acute lethal organ injury (for example, acute myocardial infarction, acute coronary syndrome, acute pulmonary embolism, or acute stroke), decompensated or end stage of chronic organ dysfunction (for example, decompensated cirrhosis, decompensated chronic renal insufficiency, severe congestive heart According to the clinical diagnosis and/or medical history on admission, the remaining cohort (n = 7,337) was divided into two groups: those with diabetes (n = 952) and those without diabetes (n = 6,385) for the sake of further research (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Study Inclusion Criteria

Data Information

An interdisciplinary study team consisting of physicians, data scientists, and statisticians examined the medical records of patients as part of their investigation. After a process of deidentification, in which the personal information of the participants (such as their name and ID) was removed and they were designated using a coding system, the fundamental information, epidemiological records, clinical manifestations, laboratory findings, radiographic characteristics from CT, treatments, and outcomes while the patients were hospitalized were recorded. We took note of

the most important clinical signs, including fever, cough, weariness, dyspnea, and comorbidities. The findings from the laboratory comprised a routine blood test, blood glucose levels before and after a meal (fasting and postprandial), C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin, D-dimer, and serum indicators for liver impairment, kidney injury, and heart dysfunction. In order to ensure that the results were reliable, an expert medical team investigated, interpreted, and validated each piece of data twice.

Propensity Score-Matched Analysis

The propensity score-matching (PSM) method was used to address the variables that could potentially obfuscate the connection between BG and the outcomes of COVID-19 (Waljee et al., 2013). PSM demands a full set of variables for each and every patient; as a result, randomly missing values of 10 selected parameters from noninvasive tests were assumed to be correct. It was determined that the non-parameter imputation method missForest should be used, and the imputation error was estimated to be 4.08 percent. After adding 10 percent more parameters at random, the bootstrapped cross validation was utilized once again and carried out a total of ten times in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the imputation procedure on the training data. When parameters were added, the missForest approach produced differences in the datasets that ranged from 4.11 percent to 5.44 percent (interquartile range: 1.91 percent to 4.11 percent).

Quantification and Statistical Analysis

R-3.6.3 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria) and SPSS Statistics were utilized for every statistical analysis (version 23.0, IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Data with continuous variables were displayed as median and interquartile range (IQR), whilst data with categorical variables were displayed as frequency rates and percentages (percent). Continuous variables were compared between two groups using Student's t tests (normally distributed) or the Mann-Whitney U test (nonnormally distributed). Using Fisher's exact test or the 2 test, categorical variables were compared. The link between the median of blood glucose and parameters associated to viral infection or glycemic control in diabetic patients was evaluated using a generalized linear model (GLM). The risk for composite endpoints and associated hazard ratio (HR) were assessed using the Cox proportional hazard model and the Cox mixed-effect model. The cumulative mortality rates were displayed using the Kaplan-Meier method. Considered statistically significant was a difference with a two-sided of less than 0.05.

Results

Clinical Characteristics of Patients with COVID-19 and Pre-existing T2D upon Admission

Out of the 9,663 confirmed instances of COVID-19, clinic characteristics were gathered from a total of 7,337 individuals, including 952 subjects with pre-existing T2D (n = 510 male, 53.6%) and 6,385 non-diabetic cases (n = 2,967 male, 46.5%). (Figure 2). 2,326 COVID-19 cases out of the initial 9,663 cases enrolled were excluded from the study, including 1,013 patients who were younger than 18 or older than 75 years old, 872 patients without complete medical records, 13 patients who had an acute myocardial infarction, 5 patients who had an acute coronary syndrome, 8 patients who had an acute pulmonary embolism, 10 patients who had an acute stroke, 11 patients who had an acute severe pancreatitis, 9 patients with cirrhosis. The prevalence of T2D was 13.0 percent from the final cohort of 7,337 COVID-19 patients examined, which was comparable to the countrywide prevalence of T2D in China (approximately 10.9 percent) (Wang et al., 2017). In the diabetes and non-diabetic groups, the median ages were 62 (55-68) and 53 (40-63) respectively (Table S1). Patients with or without T2D had median body mass indices (BMI) of 24.7 (22.0-26.4) and 23.4 (21.0-26.0), respectively. For both groups, the median time from the onset of symptoms to admission was 10 days (6-19). Similar to the overall patient population, both groups' most common symptoms were fever (71.8%), cough (63.5%), fatigue (32.3%), and dyspnea (16.1%). In comparison to the non-diabetic group, patients with T2D experienced significantly greater rates

of fatigue (38.0 percent against 31.4 percent) and dyspnea (20.5 percent versus 15.4 percent). In the T2D group compared to the non-diabetic group, there were higher frequencies of pre-existing hypertension (53.4 percent versus 19.7 percent), coronary heart disease (CHD; 13.7 percent versus 3.7 percent), cerebrovascular disease (5.6 percent versus 1.5 percent), and chronic kidney disease (4.9 percent versus 1.3 percent). According to chest CT scans, patients with diabetes had a greater incidence of bilateral lung lesions (88.1 percent versus 80.4 percent) than patients without diabetes.

Heart rate and breathing rate were the same in the diabetic and non-diabetic groups. However, the diabetic group had slightly higher systolic blood pressure (130 mmHg [120–142] vs. 126 mmHg [120–136]). As expected, the diabetic group had much higher levels of blood glucose (BG) than the non-diabetic group (8.3 mmol/L [6.2–12.4] vs. 5.2 mmol/L [4.7–6.1]), along with higher levels of HbA1c (7.9 percent [6.8 percent–9.5 percent] vs. 6.1 percent [5.7 percent–6.6 percent]). Compared to people without T2D, patients with T2D had a much higher rate of lymphopenia (44.5 percent vs. 32.6 percent) and a higher ratio of elevated leukocyte (11.3 percent vs. 6.6 percent) and neutrophil (17.2 percent vs. 9.9 percent) counts in their peripheral blood. At the same time, the T2D group was more likely to have elevated serum markers of inflammation (C-reactive protein, CRP [57.0% versus 42.4%] and procalcitonin [33.3% versus 20.3%]), decreased kidney function (creatinine [12.0% versus 5%]), and increased coagulation status (D-dimer [50.5% versus 33.3%]) than the non-diabetic group. Also, the diabetic group was more likely than the non-diabetic group to have a SpO₂ of less than 95% when they were admitted (18.8% vs. 13.2%).

Patients with COVID-19 and Pre-existing T2D Require More Intensive In-Hospital Treatment

The patients with pre-existing T2D received significantly more intensive integrated treatments to manage their symptoms of COVID-19 than the non-diabetic subjects. The former group registered a higher need for antibiotics (61.3% versus 56.9%), antifungal drugs (2.5% versus 1.2%), systemic corticosteroids (29.4% versus 22.8%), immunoglobulin (23.0% versus 17.7%), anti-hypertensive drug (45.1% versus 21.1%), and even vasoactive drugs (7.7% versus 2.2%). Oxygen inhalation (76.9% versus 61.2%), noninvasive ventilation (10.2% versus 3.9%), and invasive ventilation (3.6% versus 0.7%) were also applied significantly more frequently to the individuals with T2D compared to the patients without T2D (Table 1).

Table 1: In-Hospital Management of Patients with COVID-19 in the Well-Controlled or Poorly Controlled BG Group

Management	Total (N = 810)	Well Controlled (n = 282)	Poorly Controlled (n = 528)	p Value ^b
Traditional Chinese medicine (%)	650 (80.3%)	235 (83.3%)	415 (78.6%)	0.129
Antiviral drug, n (%)	553 (68.3%)	177 (62.8%)	376 (71.2%)	0.017
Antibiotics drug, n (%)	501 (61.9%)	150 (53.2%)	351 (66.5%)	<0.001
Systemic corticosteroids, n (%)	241 (29.8%)	57 (20.2%)	184 (34.9%)	<0.001
Immunoglobulin, n (%)	183 (22.6%)	43 (15.3%)	140 (26.5%)	<0.001
Anti-hypertensive drug, n (%)	380 (46.9%)	128 (45.4%)	252 (47.7%)	0.575
Lipid-lowering drug, n (%)	126 (15.6%)	40 (14.2%)	86 (16.3%)	0.493
Vasoactive drug, n (%)	54 (6.7%)	7 (2.5%)	47 (8.9%)	0.001
Antifungal medications, n (%)	16 (2.0%)	1 (0.4%)	15 (2.8%)	0.031
Metformin, n (%)	278 (34.3%)	76 (27.0%)	202 (38.3%)	0.002
Sulfonylurea, n (%)	106 (13.1%)	22 (7.8%)	84 (15.9%)	0.002
DPP-4 inhibitor, n (%)	55 (6.8%)	11 (3.9%)	44 (8.3%)	0.025
Insulin, n (%)	328 (40.5%)	40 (14.2%)	288 (54.6%)	<0.001
Alpha-glucosidase inhibitor, n (%)	337 (41.6%)	90 (31.9%)	247 (46.8%)	<0.001
Trizaolidinedione, n (%)	9 (1.1%)	2 (0.7%)	7 (1.3%)	0.508
Meglitide	35 (4.3%)	7 (2.5%)	28 (5.3%)	0.089
Oxygen inhalation, n (%)	639 (78.9%)	198 (70.2%)	441 (83.5%)	<0.001
Noninvasive ventilation, n (%) ^a	76 (9.4%)	13 (4.6%)	63 (11.9%)	0.001
Invasive ventilation, n (%) ^a	22 (2.7%)	0 (0.0%)	22 (4.2%)	0.001
Renal replacement therapy, n (%)	15 (1.9%)	5 (1.8%)	10 (1.9%)	1.000
Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation, n (%) ^a	4 (0.5%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (0.8%)	0.304

T2D is linked to all-cause mortality and harmful comorbidities in COVID-19 patients

During the 28-day follow-up period, we performed a retrospective longitudinal analysis on various parameters starting from the time of admission to the hospital for each patient in the study. We noticed that, despite having received more aggressive treatment against COVID-19 and the comorbidities, the diabetic group had greater incidences of decreased lymphocyte counts and increased neutrophil counts, as well as higher levels of serum interleukin-6 (IL-6), CRP, and lactic dehydrogenase (LDH), accompanied by higher BG levels, compared to the non-diabetic group. The BG level was also significantly associated with comorbid hypertension, CHD, the incidences of decreased lymphocyte count, and elevated neutrophil count and the levels of serum CRP and creatinine in the entire cohort (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Kaplan-Meier Curves for cumulative probability of COVID-19 mortality during 28-day follow-up duration in T2D and non-T2D cohorts. The blips indicate censoring.

During the 28-day follow-up period beginning with admission, the in-hospital death rate was considerably greater in patients who had previously been diagnosed with T2D compared to non-diabetic individuals (7.8 percent versus 2.7 percent, p 0.001) (Table 2).

Table 2. Incidence for primary and secondary outcomes in T2D and non-T2D groups

Outcomes	Total (N=7337)	T2D (n=952)	Non-T2D (n=6385)	P value ^a
All-cause mortality, n (%)	248(3.4%)	74(7.8%)	174(2.7%)	<0.001
Septic shock, n (%)	76(1.3%)	27(3.8%)	49(1.0%)	<0.001
ARDS, n (%)	622(8.5%)	161(16.9%)	461(7.2%)	<0.001
DIC, n (%)	18(0.3%)	5(0.5%)	13(0.2%)	0.074
Acute kidney injury, n (%)	86(1.2%)	37(3.9%)	49(0.8%)	<0.001
Acute heart injury, n (%)	260(3.5%)	69(7.3%)	191(3.0%)	<0.001

Abbreviations: ARDS, Acute respiratory distress syndrome; DIC, disseminated intravascular coagulation.

a, The P value was calculated by Fisher's exact test or χ^2 test.

The diabetes group had a crude HR of 2.90 for the 28-day all-cause death rate, which was significantly higher than the non-diabetic persons (95 percent confidence interval [CI], 2.21–3.81; p 0.001) (Table S4). After taking into account factors such as age, gender, and the location of the hospital where the patient was admitted, the HR for the overall mortality rate between these two groups was 1.70 (95 percent confidence interval: 1.29–2.24; p 0.001) (Table 3).

Table 3. Hazard Ratio for primary and secondary outcome in T2D and non-T2D groups

T2D vs non-T2D	Unadjusted		Adjusted ^a		Adjusted ^b	
	HR(95%CI)	P value	HR(95%CI)	P value ^c	HR(95%CI)	P value ^c
All-cause mortality	2.90(2.21,3.81)	<0.001	1.70(1.29,2.24)	<0.001	1.49(1.13,1.96)	0.005
Septic shock	3.66(2.25,5.95)	<0.001	2.43(1.48,3.99)	<0.001	1.95(1.18,3.20)	0.009
ARDS	2.47(2.06,2.95)	<0.001	1.71(1.42,2.06)	<0.001	1.44(1.20,1.73)	<0.001
DIC	2.58(0.92,7.23)	0.072	1.40(0.49,3.94)	0.529	1.28(0.45,3.64)	0.644
Acute kidney injury	5.11(3.33,7.83)	<0.001	3.43(2.21,5.34)	<0.001	3.01(1.94,4.68)	<0.001
Acute heart injury	2.47(1.87,3.25)	<0.001	1.53(1.16,2.03)	0.003	1.32(0.99,1.74)	0.055

Abbreviations: ARDS, Acute respiratory distress syndrome; DIC, disseminated intravascular coagulation; HR, Hazard ratio; CI, Confidence interval.

a, The adjusted variables included age and gender, hospital sites (as a random effect).

b, The adjusted variables included age, gender, indicators of the severity of COVID-19, hospital sites (as a random effect).

c, The P values were calculated based on Cox proportional hazard model.

After further adjusting for the severity of COVID-19, we discovered that the HR for all-cause mortality was 1.49 between these two groups (95 percent confidence interval: 1.13–1.96; p = 0.005). (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Distribution of glycemic variability in the well-controlled BG control group and the poorly-controlled BG control group

We did not make any adjustments for comorbidities that are closely associated with type 2 diabetes, such as hypertension, coronary heart disease, cerebrovascular illness, or chronic renal disease; these disorders frequently co-exist with type 2 diabetes.

In addition, those with type 2 diabetes were more likely to experience ARDS (16.9 percent as opposed to 7.2 percent), acute heart injury (7.3 percent as opposed to 3.0 percent), acute kidney injury (3.9 percent as opposed to 0.8 percent),

septic shock (3.8 percent as opposed to 1.0 percent), and disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) (0.5 percent as opposed to 0.2 percent) (Table S3). Mixed-effect Cox analysis showed that type 2 diabetes had a significant correlation with the occurrence of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), acute kidney injury (AKI), and septic shock, with respective adjusted HRs of 1.44 (95 percent confidence interval [CI], 1.20–1.73), 3.01 (95 percent CI, 1.94–4.68), and 1.95 (95 percent CI, 1.18–3.20). This was the case after adjusting for age, gender, and the severity of COVID-19 (Table S4). Our current analysis was based on the largest diabetic COVID-19 cohort that has so far been studied, and the results were unequivocal to implicate diabetes mellitus in a higher risk of death and other adverse consequences of the COVID-19 study. It is important to note that extreme caution is required when interpreting the statistically significant difference in outcomes between diabetic and non-diabetic patients who were treated with COVID-19. This is due to the fact that there were significant differences in the covariate distributions between the two groups.

Discussion

Thrombocytopenia and leukopenia are more common in patients with severe COVID-19 illness [7], while lymphocytopenia and thrombocytopenia are more common on arrival. As a result, higher levels of interleukin-6 (IL-6) and C-reactive protein, as well as higher d-dimer concentrations, were found to be linked with severity [7], [26]. There is an unbalance between increasing levels of bleeding factors and the relative suppression of fibrinolytic activity that occurs in T2DM, in addition to the already well-documented inflammatory process. Endothelial dysfunction and increased platelet aggregation and activation are linked to insulin resistance and T2DM. As a result of these anomalies, a hypercoagulable pro-thrombotic condition might arise [19]. Other chronic illnesses, such as hypertension and cardiovascular disease (CVD), are similarly influenced by atherosclerosis, vascular inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction [22]. SARS-CoV-infected animals showed reduced T-cell and B-cell activity, as well as increased inflammatory markers, as a result of aging. As a result, T2DM alone or in combination with age, hypertension, and/or cardiovascular disease (CVD) may contribute to a reduced regulation of SARS-CoV-2 replication and a longer proinflammatory response, which could lead to poor results.

Cross-species transmission of coronaviruses relies heavily on viral entrance into host cells (CoVs). Infected cells express particular receptors, which are found on the surface of all CoVs that have been exposed to the host. Virus entry and replication are made possible by the host cell protease, which cleaves the spike after attachment to target cells. Researchers have found that the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) is a key receptor for both the SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 [51, 50]. The respiratory tract, heart, kidneys, intestines, brain neurons, endothelium of arteries and veins, immunological cells, and the pancreas all have ACE2 expression. [2] Researchers in China studied 39 SARS-CoV patients who hadn't been diagnosed with diabetes prior to their hospitalization, and found that 20 of them got diabetes while in the hospital. SARS-CoV may have caused acute insulin-dependent diabetic mellitus by damaging pancreatic islets, as evidenced by the high levels of ACE2 immunostaining in these animals [22]. Patients with diabetes may be at greater risk of complications if pancreatic damage is found in COVID-19 patients, even if more proof is lacking.

When ACE medications and angiotensin receptor blockers are prolonged in patients with viral pneumonia, mortality and endotracheal intubation are reduced [13, 24]. It has been hypothesized that these drugs have strong immunomodulatory effects [55], as well as an anti-inflammatory effect on the respiratory and systemic inflammatory response [53, 54]. Their effect on the clinical course of COVID-19 has been hotly contested because they are regularly used by people with diabetes and hypertension [16]. ACEIs and ARBs have been suggested to have a negative impact

on the outcome of COVID-19 patients since ACE2 is a SARS-CoV-2 functional receptor [17]. ACEIs and ARBs, on the other hand, have some supporters who believe they may even be advantageous [58]. Infection with SARS-CoV and the Spike protein of the virus suppress the expression of ACE2. If SARS-CoV Spike was injected into mice, the acute lung failure was increased, but this could be reduced by inhibiting the renin angiotensin system [19]. Retrospective examination of 112 COVID-19 and cardiovascular disease patients found no significant difference in the prevalence of ACEI/ARB treatment between survivors and non-survivors [10]. It has been shown that ibuprofen (11), thiazolidinediones (62), and other anti-inflammatory medicines (ARBs) can also cause an elevation in ACE2, raising concerns about the safety of these medications in individuals with COVID-19.

Even while poorer results in COVID-19 patients have been linked to diabetes, people with diabetes may not be more susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection. Infected individuals have a diabetes prevalence that is comparable to, if not somewhat lower than, the overall population [28], [63]. A diabetes prevalence of 10.3% was found in a meta-analysis of 12 studies involving 2,108 Chinese patients with COVID-19 [63], which was in line with the national prevalence of 10.9 percent published in 2013 [64]. Similar results were obtained in an Italian study of individuals with proven SARS-CoV-2 infection at Padova University Hospital. Diabetes affected 8.9% of these patients (mean age 65.3 years), whereas it affected 11.0 percent of adults aged 55–75 (mean age 65 years) from the same region in 2018 [15]. Although underreporting may be a problem, it's important to keep an eye out for any biological processes. The major MERS-CoV receptor is dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) [2]. Due to the widespread use of DPP-4 inhibitors in diabetes treatment around the globe [13], [26], future studies should investigate whether DPP-4 can also act as a receptor for SARS-CoV-2, contributing to the potential protective impact of these medications against COVID-19.

Anti-CoV-2 drugs and vaccines for COVID-19 treatment have not yet been formally licensed [67]. Remdesivir, lopinavir/ritonavir, ribavirin, chloroquine phosphate, and arbidol are all currently being tested in clinical trials to determine their safety and efficacy [18]. Chloroquine and its hydroxy-analogue, hydroxychloroquine, are two interesting pharmacological options for diabetic patients. Chloroquine, a medication widely used to treat malaria and autoimmune illnesses, has also been discovered to have broad-spectrum antiviral properties. Recent research shows that chloroquine is particularly successful at controlling SARS-CoV-2 infection in vitro even if its efficiency and safety for COVID-19 treatment remain unconfirmed. Chloroquine elevates endosomal pH and interferes with glycosylation of SARS-CoV cellular receptors, preventing viral infection in addition to its immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory effects [19]. Clinical trials in China, which included over a hundred patients, have shown that chloroquine is superior to the control group in shortening the disease's course, inhibiting pneumonia exacerbation, encouraging virus negative conversion, and improving radiological results without severe side effects [10]. It has also been found that hydroxychloroquine improves glycemic control in patients with diabetes who are decompensated and treatment-resistant [21, 12]. T2DM patients who fail to meet glycemic objectives with two other oral glucose-lowering medications might now receive an additional dose of the medicine. Despite the fact that inflammation is linked to poor glucose control, the mechanism by which hydroxychloroquine works to lower blood sugar levels is yet unknown [21]. Increasing the C peptide response by chloroquine has been reported to suggest better β -cell function in the pancreas [12]. A putative side effect of hydroxychloroquine in animal models is a reduction in intracellular insulin breakdown and an increase in insulin buildup [24]. Using chloroquine/hydroxychloroquine in patients with diabetes and COVID-19 should

be done cautiously because of the previously described effects on glucose metabolism. Preventing hypoglycemia episodes may necessitate adjusting the dosage of either the oral antidiabetic medications or insulin.

In addition, the impact of corticosteroids on COVID-19 is being studied [68]. ARDS and acute lung injury are in part caused by the body's immune system. In addition to reducing pulmonary inflammation, corticosteroids have been shown to reduce immunity and pathogen clearance. Lung histopathology demonstrated inflammation and diffuse alveolar damage in SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV infections [16]. As a result, corticosteroids have been widely used. As a result of this, it has been shown to delay viral RNA clearance or increase mortality and comorbidities such as diabetes, psychosis and avascular necrosis [15]. When SARS-CoV-2 infection is suspected, corticosteroids should not be used outside of clinical trials, according to the WHO interim clinical care guidelines [19]. Corticosteroids for COVID-19 should be used with caution in people with diabetes because of their hyperglycemic effect [80] and the impact they have on the immunological response.

Patients with diabetes infected by SARS-CoV-2 and those with COVID-19 who develop glycemic decompensation have no evidence to guide their treatment. It may be possible to reduce the severity of symptoms by monitoring glucose levels and avoiding drug interactions. One should not overlook the risk of hypoglycemia episodes as a result of the interplay between pharmacological treatment, viral pathogenesis, and the regular metabolic disturbances in diabetes. Based on disease severity, the existence of concomitant conditions and diabetes-related complications, age and other variables should be developed patient-tailored therapy methods and optimal glucose control goals. Hospitalization and recuperation may necessitate the use of a multidisciplinary team approach, including infectologists and endocrinologists, pulmonologists, psychologists and nutritionists. Diabetic nephropathy and diabetes-related heart problems increase the risk of severe COVID-19 and death [7, 19]. Those with these conditions should receive special attention. Finally, better outcomes for individuals with COVID-19 may be achieved through improved vigilance and testing in outpatient diabetes clinics, as well as lower thresholds for hospitalization.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study protocol was approved by the Institution Ethic Committee

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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